

Minutes EB26-2
Meeting of the SeqCode Executive Board
11 May 2026

Maria Chuvochina (MC)	- Chair, Reconciliation Commission
Phil Hugenholtz (PH)	- Member without portfolio
Kostas Konstantinidis (KK)	- Chair, Standards Working Group
Anna-Louise Reysenbach (ALR)	- Vice Chair
Luis Miguel Rodriguez (LMR)	- Chair, Registry Working Group
Iain Sutcliffe (IS)	- Chair, Legislative Commission
Fanus Venter (FV)	- Secretary
Barny Whitman (BW)	- Chair

Apologies

Fengping Wang (FW)	- Member without portfolio
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1. Welcome

BW welcomed the members of the Executive Board.

2. Additions to the Agenda

3. Matters Arising/Action points from the previous meeting

New and ongoing action items from previous meeting

- 1. FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved. Completed.*
- 2. FV to send out a call for nominations of officials for the next term as part of the SeqCode News. Completed.*
- 3. LMR will follow-up with Thomas Hitch about the possible use of Protologger for the naming of taxa. Ongoing.*
- 4. FV to approach the BISMIS Executive Board to inquire if the BISMIS Live slot of September 2026 could be used for hosting the SeqCode plenary. Completed.*
- 5. MC, IS and FV to provide suggestions for the format of the SeqCode Community plenary meeting. Ongoing.*
- 6. IS, KK, LMR and MC to provide a short report on the activities of commissions and working groups for 2025. The reports should reach BW before the end of March. To be finalised.*
- 7. LMR and BW to prepare and submit a funding application for 2026 to the ISME office, including funding for the SeqCode prize. Completed.*
- 8. FV to follow-up with the ISME office regarding the Vice-Chair voting process. Completed, EB decided not to continue with the election. ALR to remain on the EB until the end of the term.*
- 9. LMR to investigate the possible options and processes to obtain legal protection for the SeqCode name. Ongoing.*
- 10. KK and LMR to share suggestion for minimum metadata recommendations for consideration by the board members. Ongoing.*

4. Reports from Commissions and Working Groups

Legislative Commission

The period for comments on the paratype proposal has now ended. As no comments were received, the proposal will proceed to a vote by the SeqCode Committee. It was decided that the SeqCode will manage the voting process independently as the ISME Office is currently occupied with preparations for ISME 20.

The open-source Helios voting platform, which provides verifiable online elections, will be tested and may be adopted should the EB be satisfied with its usability and management features.

Standards Working Group

KK and LMR will circulate a proposal on the minimum recommendations for metadata linked to entries of genome sequences to the EB. A decision on whether the SeqCode should be amended to formalize these requirements will then be taken.

Registry and Nomenclature Working Group

At present 1337 names have been validated, which include those of 706 species. LMR indicated that three of his students will provide support to the registry for the incorporation of Candidatus names.

Reconciliation Commission

The commission has nothing to report.

5. Membership renewal

LMR will assist with a streamlined process via the Registry for the re-registration of all SeqCode Committee members.

6. Membership Drive

The EB discussed initiating a formal membership drive to raise awareness of the benefits of the SeqCode among microbial ecologists and taxonomists, particularly those in countries such as India, Brazil, and China, where challenges may be experienced when depositing type cultures. ISME20, which will be held in Auckland, New Zealand (16–21 August 2026) will also provide an ideal opportunity to promote the SeqCode.

7. Election of the Executive Board

A new Executive Board should be elected as the term of the current board will end in December 2026. A call for nominations will again be circulated as part of the next SeqCode News. The final slate of candidates will be confirmed in September. Elections will be held around early/mid-October to ensure that the incoming officers are announced before the end of 2026. Individuals who have expressed interest in the SeqCode will also be contacted to determine their willingness to serve within its governance structures.

8. Scheduling of plenary meeting of the SeqCode Community

A plenary meeting of the SeqCode Community should be held once during the four-year term of the Executive Board. Suggestions for the format and date of the meeting will be presented at the next EB meeting by a small committee consisting of MC, IS and FV.

The BISMIS Executive Board indicated that the Seqcode could use a BISMIS Live slot to report on the progress made during the last 4 years. The date of the presentation and who will present will still be determined.

9. SeqCode Prize

Only one application was received. A number of EB members will look at the application and will then decide whether the deadline for applications should be extended.

10. Annual report

Some of the reports from the chairs of the commissions and working groups are still outstanding. These reports should reach BW by 10 May. EB members are also requested to provide comments on the draft report that has also been circulated by the same deadline.

11. Conference and Meeting Updates

EB members are encouraged to submit any relevant documents on the shared drive.

New action items

New and ongoing action items from previous meeting

1. FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.
2. FV to initiate a test run to determine if the Helios voting system is appropriate for our needs.
3. FV to initiate the voting for the paratype proposal as soon as a decision is made on the voting platform to be used.
4. LMR to assist with a streamlined process via the Registry for the re-registration of current SeqCode Committee members.
5. FV to circulate plans for a formal membership drive.
6. FV to again send out a call for nominations of officials for the next term as part of the SeqCode News.
7. EB members to decide on the extension of the SeqCode prize deadline if necessary.
8. FV to approach the BISMIS Executive Board to finalize the date of the BISMIS Live presentation.
9. EB members to provide comments and contributions for the annual report to BW by 10 May.

Ongoing items

10. LMR will follow-up with Thomas Hitch about the possible use of Protologger for the naming of taxa. Ongoing.
11. MC, IS and FV to provide suggestions for the format of the SeqCode Community plenary meeting. Ongoing.
12. LMR to investigate the possible options and processes to obtain legal protection for the SeqCode name. Ongoing.
13. KK and LMR to share suggestion for minimum metadata recommendations for consideration by the board members. Ongoing.

Minutes prepared by FV: 20 May 2026

Approved: 29 May 2026